

RESPONDENT

D7.3 – Dissemination and Communication Report 1

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Authors	Benjamin Moore		
Co-authors	Linda Henriksson		
Reviewers	Dorleta Garcia Melero (VICOM), Dimitris Asimakopoulos (KIEFER)		

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PROJECT PARTNERS

Partner	Country	Short name
FUTURE INTELLIGENCE EREVNA TILEPIKINONIAKON KE PLIROFORIAKON SYSTIMATON EPE	Greece	FINT
FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	Spain	VICOM
CARR COMMUNICATIONS LIMITED	Ireland	CARR
KIEFER TEK ETAIREIA PERIORISMENIS EFTHYNIS	Greece	KIEFER
GREENESCO ENERGEIAKI ANONYMI ETAIREIA	Greece	GREEN
ESTABANELL Y PAHISA ENERGIA SA	Spain	EPESA
FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'ENERGIA DE CATALUNYA	Spain	IREC-CERCA
ELECTROTECNICA DEL URUMEA SL	Spain	EUSKABEA

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Definition
HRB	Horizon Results Booster
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on RESPONDENT's dissemination and communication activities carried out from M1 to M15 of the project, as well as outlining planned activities that will take place up until the end of the project in M30. In addition to describing the implementation of RESPONDENT's dissemination and communication strategy, this report will also serve as a tracker and handbook to ensure maximum impact within the context of these activities is achieved.

As of January 2024, M15 of the project, RESPONDENT has developed impactful dissemination material, targeted relevant audiences, actively managed a range of online channels, and represented the project at numerous events, both virtual and in-person conferences. Project partners have actively contributed to the dissemination efforts by sharing updates on the progress and the results that are being generated. Partners have also been actively involved in the communications activities by raising awareness about the project, promoting it, and engaging targeted audiences through selected channels using tailored key messages. The project website, X (Twitter), LinkedIn, and YouTube pages have all served as platforms for raising awareness about the project and engaging with relevant stakeholders.

The communication and dissemination performance has been measured and analysed. This deliverable provides an update on the measurable targets and future impactful activities planned for the next stages of the project.

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1 Introduction

This report builds upon deliverable *D7.2 – Plan for Dissemination and Communication*, which was published in M6 of the project and based on the initial plans as described in the RESPONDENT Grant Agreement (GA).

The strategy outlined in the previous deliverable has naturally evolved since its submission in M6 of the project, and the partners have sought to update their plans as the solutions take shape and the project continues to evolve and mature. This document outlines concrete actions that were implemented to increase the impact of the project results, as well as plans for the second half of the project and its communication and dissemination strategies going forward.

A strategy for communication and dissemination is inherently dynamic, meaning that it evolves and can be reshaped to align with potential changes in priorities. Expanding on D7.2, this report provides an update on the communication and dissemination landscape surrounding the project.

The first part of this deliverable will focus on the dissemination achievements, which include events, publications, and networking and clustering activities. The second part will analyse performance of communication channels and activities. The last part of this report will outline the proposed next steps to ensure that the project is given maximum visibility and that relevant stakeholders continue to be informed about the project and the results.

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to serve as a tracker and handbook for the dissemination and communication activities of RESPONDENT, as well as an interim report of the work carried out so far. The implementation of the plan for dissemination and communication is continuously monitored throughout the lifecycle of the project, with the purpose of this report being to provide a detailed picture of its status at M15.

Furthermore, this report will outline the next steps of our dissemination and communication plan that will ensure maximum visibility and that relevant target audiences are informed of the project and, in particular, its results, as the project naturally progresses into a more results-orientated phase.

1.2 Intended readership

This deliverable will be disseminated both internally amongst the project consortium members, and externally to any interested parties outside of the project should they wish to view it. The intended readership primarily concerns members of the RESPONDENT consortium, the European Commission RESPONDENT Project Officer, European agencies and other H2020 and Horizon Europe projects working in the field of renewable energy and climate mitigation.

As this is a public deliverable, it is openly accessible to all external stakeholders in the [Deliverables](#) section of the project website.

This deliverable will be of particular interest to the project partners, as it serves as an instrument to help partners to keep track of all communication and dissemination activities, as well as assisting them in where they stand and how they can contribute to maximise the impact of the project.

1.3 Relationship with other RESPONDENT deliverables

This deliverable is closely linked to the deliverables listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Relationship between D7.3 and other RESPONDENT deliverables

Deliverable	Name of Deliverable	Link to D7.3
D7.1	RESPONDENT Website	As D7.1 established the project's profile and brand to external entities and the website serves as the nucleus for all dissemination activities.
D7.2	Plan for Dissemination and Communication	D7.3 monitors the execution of RESPONDENT's plan for dissemination and communication (D7.2)
D7.4	Dissemination and Communication Report 2	D7.4 will monitor the execution of RESPONDENT's communication and dissemination strategy (D7.2)

The information and figures related to dissemination that are reported in this deliverable were gathered in between mid and late January of 2024, and therefore reflect the status up until that point. The following subsections will provide details on the specific actions that have been carried out under each type of dissemination activity.

2.2 Performance Measurement and Analysis

When it comes to dissemination and communication activities, measuring and monitoring its performance and success can be challenging, as not all success factors are tangible. In other words, not all elements leading to impactful dissemination and communication can be quantified or distilled into a single document. While keeping this challenge in mind, the performance is regularly measured against the agreed key performance indicators (KPIs). The dissemination KPIs and numerical targets listed in Table 2 facilitate the measuring of how well the project is thus far achieving its dissemination goals.

Table 2: Dissemination KPIs

Category	Activity	Target Y1 (M12)	Target Y2 (M24)	Target Y3	Status at M15
Scientific excellence of project research	Open access, peer reviewed scientific publications	0	1	2	In progress
	Conference presentations	2	4	6	In progress: 1 in Y1 and 1 in Y2
	White Paper	0	0	1	In progress
Community Engagement	Host at least 2 workshops	1	1	1	In progress: First workshop held in Y1
	Host at least 1 public webinar	0	0	1	In progress
	Attend at least 1 trade fair	0	0	1	In progress
Pilots	3 events – 1 per pilot and 1 at the end of the project	0	1	2	In progress

2.3 Publications

As of M15, the RESPONDENT project has deliberately prioritised foundational research for its proposed solutions and the establishment of a robust framework in its inaugural year, resulting in a temporary absence of publications in peer-reviewed journals or conference presentations. This intentional emphasis on laying a strong groundwork is a testament to the project's commitment to ensuring a solid foundation for future endeavours and efforts to have RESPONDENT's research and results widely disseminated among the key stakeholders that it has identified.

As the project enters its second year, the intention of RESPONDENT is to strategically transition from preparatory activities to a more active stage of implementation, with a strong focus on disseminating its findings widely. The consortium is now gearing up to share tangible results through peer-reviewed journals and conference presentations. This shift aligns with RESPONDENT's commitment to open science principles, demonstrating a clear trajectory towards the realisation and generation of substantial outcomes.

Looking ahead, the consortium has collectively agreed to intensify efforts on publishing results in scientific journals and other relevant publications during the second half of the project. This move reflects our confidence in the upcoming milestones and underscores our dedication to actively contributing valuable insights to the scientific community.

A selection of publications, as identified by all members of the Consortium, to be targeted is presented below in Table 3.

Table 3: Selection of Targeted Journals

Journal title	Publisher	Homepage
Citizen Science: Theory and Practice	Ubiquity Press	https://theoryandpractice.citizenscienceassociation.org/
Energies	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	https://www.mdpi.com/
European Journal of Electrical Engineering & Computer Science (EJECE)	European Open Science	https://www.ejece.org/index.php/ejece
European Journal of	European Open Science	https://www.ej-energy.org/index.php/ejenergy

Energy Research		
IEEE Transactions on Power Systems	IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=59
IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid	IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=5165411
IET Smart Grid	Wiley	https://ietresearch.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/hub/journal/25152947/homepage/productinformation.html
International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation	Elsevier Ltd.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-applied-earth-observation-and-geoinformation
International Journal of Energy Research	Wiley	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/1099114x
International Journal of Environmental Monitoring and Analysis (IJEMA)	Science Publishing Group	https://www.sciencepublishinggroup.com/i/ijema
Renewable Energy	Elsevier Ltd.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/renewable-energy
Smart Energy	IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/smart-energy?_gl=1*_9shvwf*_ga*Mzk5MDA2OTI1LjE2Nzk0ODkxODQ.*_ga_4R527DM8F7*MTY3OTQ4OTE4NC4xLjAuMTY3OTQ4OTE4NC4wLjAuMA..
Sustainability	MDPI	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability
Sustainable Energy, Grids	Elsevier Ltd.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/sustainable-energy-grids-and-networks

and Networks (SEGAN)		
The International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems (JEPE)	Elsevier Ltd.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-electrical-power-and-energy-systems

As stated in deliverable *D7.2 – Communication and Dissemination Plan*, RESPONDENT is strongly committed to promoting open science research, and all the scientific articles and conference papers produced will be published according to the Horizon Europe Open Access guidelines and made publicly available. Special arrangements will be made to guarantee the security and confidentiality of restricted information.

With the aim of further facilitating the visibility of RESPONDENT publications, a dedicated RESPONDENT project community was created on Zenodo. The RESPONDENT Zenodo community, as depicted in the below figure, has been managed and updated by the Dissemination Manager (CARR). The RESPONDENT Zenodo community is available to view here:

https://zenodo.org/communities/respondent_eu?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

Figure 2: RESPONDENT on Zenodo

By having a presence on Zenodo, this increases the potential benefits for the project’s results including increased use and direct reach with research communities working in a variety of relevant fields. Additionally, Zenodo automatically creates a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to each piece of material uploaded to the platform which will make the project’s research citable.

2.4 Events

A list of events that RESPONDENT has been represented at by M15 are listed in the table below. The events included both virtual and in-person workshops, conferences, webinars, and exhibitions.

As tangible results begin to materialise, the consortium partners envision intensified participation in a diverse array of events across Europe. An expanded presence in workshops, conferences, webinars, and exhibitions is anticipated, reflecting our dedication to actively sharing insights and contributing to relevant communities.

Table 4: RESPONDENT Attendance at Events

No	Date	Name of Event	Type of Event	Partner Involved	Presentation Title (if any)	Location	Website / Source
1	17/3/23	Copernicus Thematic Workshop: Energy	Workshop	Estabanell	N/A	Physical	https://euspa.blum.it/event/ar/3/euspa-copernicus-online-event
2	11/6/23	Skills for Clear Communication of Sustainability	Webinar	CARR	N/A	Virtual	https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/environment-and-climate/european-green-deal/green-deal-projects-support/green-deal-resources/skills-clear-communication-sustainability

3	25/6/23 – 29/6/23	PowerTech Belgrade 2023	Conference	IREC	N/A	Physical	https://powertech2023.com/
4	7/9/23	2022 National Energy Balance Report	Webinar	CARR	N/A	Virtual	https://www.linkedin.com/events/linkedinlive-2022nationalenergy7103351694809337856/theater/
5	11/9/23	Cross- promotion Call with Related Projects	Video call	CARR	Opportunities for cross- promotion of projects under HORIZON- EUSPA-2021- SPACE-02-51	Virtual	Microsoft Teams
6	26/9/23	Enlit On The Road Athens	Conference	FINT	Introduction to RESPONDENT	Physical	https://www.enlit.world/enlit-on-the-road/athens/
7	28/11/23 – 30/11/23	Enlit Europe	Exhibition	FINT, Vicomtech, and Anell	Introduction to RESPONDENT	Physical	https://www.enlit-europe.com/

2.5 Media and Multipliers

Media are an important audience in their own right, as well as being a multiplier and amplifier channel to reach other priority audience groups.

In Y1, a media contacts database was created by CARR. The database lists EU level, international and a selection of Ireland + UK based media outlets and media contacts' names and email addresses. As this database contains personal data, it is not shared publicly but is stored in CARR's internal servers. CARR also made partners aware of the possibility to avail of media training where needed.

As with RESPONDENT publications, engagement with media will intensify in the next months of the project. Press releases will be issued for all upcoming RESPONDENT events and major conference presentations. Other planned activities include pitching potential interview ideas with project partners and drafting articles for pitching to publications, both nationally and internationally, specialising in the fields of renewable energy and space-based solutions/technologies that support the initiatives of the EU's decarbonisation efforts.

Press releases will be translated and issued to media with contact information of the local project partner. As the work on the RESPONDENT solution suite progresses to the next stages, media engagement and activities will become increasingly result-oriented, promoting the developments of RESPONDENT's novel approach to supporting the ambitions of the Green Deal.

Media channels and multipliers also have the potential to serve as powerful tools for promoting the economic benefits and climate change mitigation solutions offered by the RESPONDENT project. By crafting targeted press releases and articles that highlight the cost-effectiveness and environmental advantages of the project's outputs, we can reach potential stakeholders effectively in this way. Additionally, we will continue to leverage our social media platforms to share success stories, data-driven insights, and infographics showcasing the tangible benefits of adopting the RESPONDENT solution. Through strategic media engagement, we can highlight how RESPONDENT contributes to both economic growth and climate resilience, ultimately attracting stakeholders that are keen on investing in RESPONDENT's innovative sustainable energy solutions.

It is worth noting that RESPONDENT currently has two publications pending release: an article with [Smart Energy International](#) on the project, and a general post on the project from Enlit Europe following our attendance at their event in Paris in November 2024. It is hoped that both of these pieces will be published in early 2024 and will be widely disseminated amongst our project's target audiences and key stakeholders via our website and social media profiles.

2.6 Newsletters

The RESPONDENT newsletter, which has been published on a biannual basis, provides regular updates on the project's progress and results, past and upcoming events, meetings, milestones, and more.

As of M15, two editions of the newsletter have been produced using LinkedIn's newsletter feature, with a third scheduled to be published in June 2024. An image from the second edition of the newsletter, published in December 2023, is presented below.

Figure 3: RESPONDENT Newsletter

The RESPONDENT Newsletter is compliant with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The Newsletter subscription option is open to all LinkedIn users. It is also shown to first-tier connections of the RESPONDENT LinkedIn page with an option to subscribe.

The subscription process for readers of the newsletter is straightforward. If a reader is a LinkedIn user, they can subscribe by clicking on the link in the newsletter. In case a reader does not have a LinkedIn account, they can view and read the newsletter, but they will not be able to subscribe. Therefore, the process does require the user to have a LinkedIn account, but it does not require visiting a different third-party website to sign-up, making it homogenous with their everyday social media use. When the RESPONDENT Newsletter is published, an automatic notification is sent to subscribers. Furthermore, when a LinkedIn member starts following the RESPONDENT LinkedIn page, a notification inviting them to subscribe to the newsletter is automatically sent. These functionalities increase awareness of the project and help to gain new followers on the RESPONDENT LinkedIn page.

LinkedIn’s own metrics from the newsletters enable us to measure the number of views, the engagement rate, and to view some demographic parameters, such as the type of sectors that the subscribers work in.

Table 5: RESPONDENT Newsletter Analytics

RESPONDENT Newsletter Analytics (M8-M14)

<i>Published newsletters</i>	2 Newsletter #1 (M8) Newsletter #2 (M14)
<i>Number of subscribers</i>	93 (M15)
<i>Article views</i>	160

<i>Page engagement</i>	6.5%
<i>Subscribers (sectors)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Engineering Program and Project Management Media and Communications

2.7 Dissemination through clustering, networking, and knowledge transfer activities

Clustering, networking, and knowledge sharing activities are useful procedures to help ensure the success of a project's dissemination efforts.

At the project's initiation and in earlier deliverables, our ambitions were outlined to strategically leverage clustering and networking opportunities. We aimed to foster collaboration with research and innovation projects and engage relevant stakeholders in the fields of climate change, renewable energy sources, machine learning, AI algorithms, and power grid infrastructure.

The initial half of RESPONDENT primarily focused on foundational work, including data gathering, algorithm creation, and extensive research activities. Despite our strategic vision for collaboration, the project's current phase has been predominantly dedicated to core development tasks. In terms of the dissemination activities, this has meant predominantly establishing our own brand and voice across our social media channels.

In October of 2023, the project contacted other projects under the same call as RESPONDENT, HORIZON-EUSPA-2021-SPACE, to discuss cross-promotion through various channels, such as LinkedIn and Twitter, in order to enhance our respective projects' reach, engagement, and influence. Following on from this, RESPONDENT was invited by one of the projects to participate in the Horizon Results Booster (HRB) services, managed by ICONS, the communication, dissemination, and exploitation expert appointed by the European Commission.

As part of this HRB service, we are currently in the process of coordinating further joint activities in ongoing services by the program and segmenting internal DEC deliverables and clustering milestones.

Acknowledging the importance of networking and collaboration, we are committed to further intensifying our efforts in networking and collaboration. Recognising the potential for impactful partnerships, we will actively seek engagement with relevant projects and stakeholders in our designated areas as the project solutions begin to take shape and come to fruition. The next reporting period will thus see a deliberate shift towards building partnerships and leveraging existing networks to ensure a broader impact and wider adoption of our technologies.

2.8 Management and administration of dissemination activities

The WP7 leader and Dissemination Manager CARR is responsible for the planning, creation, and development of the communication and dissemination strategy and activities. However, all partners are responsible for contributing to the communication and dissemination efforts. All partners are informed about the

management and administration of the dissemination activities through the monthly WP7 calls and emails. Relevant files are saved in a dedicated WP7 folder on the shared Google Drive, where all partners can view and download them. The coordinator and specific partners are consulted on specific issues when it is deemed to be necessary.

Details on the rules around dissemination procedures and dissemination reporting are available in the deliverable *D7.2 - Plan for Dissemination and Communication*, which was published in M6 of the project.

All partners report any dissemination actions to CARR by inserting the activities into the Dissemination Tracker excel worksheet, available to all partners via the shared Google Drive. This tracker is maintained and regularly updated by CARR, and currently includes 8 sections:

1. Events Attended
2. Future Events
3. Published Publications
4. Relevant Journal Publications
5. Media Coverage
6. Articles Generated by Partners
7. Key Stakeholders
8. Theses

3 Communication Activities

This section describes how the communication strategy of the RESPONDENT project has been implemented and performed between M1 and M15, as well as presenting the main communication activities to date. The communication strategy that was devised behind these activities ensures that these actions have and will continue to be implemented in a strategic and effective manner, creating engaging and informative content.

Section 4, Next Steps, will then outline the plans for the second half of the project from M15-M30.

3.1 Overview of Activities M1-M15

Communication activities have been continuous across all RESPONDENT platforms since the beginning of the project in November 2022. The core activities thus far have included website updates, consistent posting across Twitter and LinkedIn, YouTube videos, newsletters, blog posts, promotional material, branding, communications through events, and stakeholder engagement.

Project partners have been actively involved in raising awareness about the project, promoting it to identified stakeholders, and engaging targeted audiences through selected channels using tailored key messages. The figures reported in this deliverable were gathered between mid and late January 2024, and therefore reflect the status at M15.

3.2 Performance Measurement and Analysis

The communications performance of the project is measured and analysed on a regular basis. Communications activities, measurable targets and the current status are listed in Table 6. As the figures demonstrate, the project is on track to reach the ambitious targets, and in several areas the targets have already been exceeded.

Table 6: Communication KPIs

Category	Activity	Target Y1 (M12)	Target Y2 (M24)	Target Y3 (M30)	Status at M15
Visibility of the project at European and global level	Project website	Launch website	Continuously update the website	Update on the research and results of the project	Continuous
	Visits to the project website	2,600	5,200	8,000	1,290 ¹
	Downloads from the project website	25	50	100	28
	Number of articles in blogs/magazines/news	5	10	20	2 pending publication
Promotion of the project identity	Create project identity and branding	Create project branding and identity. Final logo and colour scheme	Revise branding and identity as required by project partners	Revise branding and Identity as required by project partners	Continuous
	Design dissemination materials	Promotional materials: leaflet/ brochure, poster, and pull-up	Update materials according to project progress	Update materials according to project progress	Leaflet and pull-up designed and printed in M12
	Project Videos (number)	1	3	6	6

¹ Figure lower than anticipated due to Google Analytics glitch, as mentioned on Page 23.

					Achieved, ongoing
	Blog + News Events Posts	10	20	30	Ongoing; 11 as of M15
Presence on social media	Implement effective social media strategy	- LinkedIn: 75 Followers - X (Twitter): 250 Followers - YouTube: 2 live videos	- LinkedIn: 150 Followers - X (Twitter): 500 Followers - YouTube: 4 live videos	- LinkedIn: 200 Followers - X (Twitter): 800 Followers - YouTube: 6 live videos	- LinkedIn: 285 Followers - X (Twitter): 434 Followers YouTube: 6 live videos

RESPONDENT's communication performance is measured and analysed both quantitatively and qualitatively.

The quantitative data acquired through analytics tools provides insights into the number and frequency of the activities carried out. The data includes metrics on website traffic, engagement, and demographics. For the social channels, analytics data is gathered on the number of followers, page views and visitors, post engagements, impressions, and shares.

The analytics used are Matomo Analytics (and Google Analytics for the first months of the project) for the website, X's own analytics for the X page, YouTube's own analytics for the YouTube page, and LinkedIn's own analytics for the LinkedIn page. Website and social media metrics are presented separately for each platform in section 3.3 Digital Communication Channels. All followers across RESPONDENT's social media channels, Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube, as well as subscribers to the newsletter, have been acquired organically and not through any sponsorship or promotion.

The collection of qualitative data is ongoing and will be thoroughly analysed in *Deliverable D7.4 – Dissemination and Communication Report 2*.

3.3 Digital Communication Channels

3.3.1 The RESPONDENT Website

The RESPONDENT website (<https://respondent-project.eu/>) serves as the nucleus of online dissemination for the project, while the social media channels are used to amplify and multiply the key messages, updates, and information published on the website.

The website is a powerful dissemination tool and a key element of engagement with target audiences of the project. The project website incorporates the visual identity of RESPONDENT and the project branding, as well as providing easy access to well-presented, non-confidential information about the project.

The landing page of the project website is presented in the figure below.

Figure 4: Website landing page

Since launching in M3 of the project, the RESPONDENT website has grown and developed significantly. New static sections have been added and the dynamic news & events section keeps growing as new posts and blog pieces are published on a regular basis.

New sections that have been added since the launch of the website include the ‘Downloads’ section, where all public deliverables up to M15 have been published and will continue to be until the end of the project. A ‘Dissemination Materials’ category was also added to the Downloads section in M14, which currently features our project logo, fact sheet, pull up banner, brochure, and brand guidelines.

Lastly, a ‘Sister’s Project’ page was created in M12. The creation of this page followed networking efforts with other projects under the same call as RESPONDENT, HORIZON-EUSPA-2021-SPACE, with the aim of fostering collaboration, sharing resources, and maximising visibility of both RESPONDENT and its sister projects.

Google Analytics was activated on 31st January, 2023, when the project website officially launched. However, due to a temporary technical glitch in the website analytics tool, the tracking of the traffic to the pages was disrupted for a number of months. The number of page visits indicated is therefore based on available data.

Matomo Analytics was then activated for the website in August of 2023 in order to comply with EU Policy criteria and ensure GDPR compliance, as it has been recommended as a viable alternative to Google Analytics by ethics experts.

Traffic to the website, which is presented in Figure 4, is set to increase further in the second half of the project as results are generated and interest in the project naturally increases.

Table 7: Website analytics

Website analytics January 2023 – January 2024 (M3-M15)

<i>Total Website Visits</i>	743
<i>Total Page Views</i>	1,290 (M15)
<i>Downloads</i>	28
<i>Top Pages by View</i>	#1 Home Page

Visits Over Time

3.3.2 X (Twitter)

The RESPONDENT X (Twitter) account has experienced a steady growth since its creation in M1 of the project, and can be viewed here: https://twitter.com/RESPONDENT_EU.

RESPONDENT's page on X primarily serves as a platform for raising awareness about the project and its progress among key stakeholders, to interact and build relationships with them, disseminate project news and results, as well as share interesting news in fields relevant to the work and research of the consortium.

An overview of the RESPONDENT X page performance is presented in the below figures, as well as a screenshot of the profile home page. The number of followers at M15 currently stands at 434, meaning that we have made good progress towards our KPI of 800 to be reached by the end of the project. At the same time, RESPONDENT's engagement rate on X is high at 4.95%, calculated as the total number of engagements a tweet receives divided by the total number of impressions on that tweet. An engagement rate of more than 1% is considered high [1]. This figure indicates that RESPONDENT's content is engaging and impactful.

Figure 5: RESPONDENT's X (Twitter) profile

Table 8: X (Twitter) analytics

X (Twitter) analytics November 2022 – January 2024 (M1-M15)

<i>Number of Followers</i>	434
<i>Number of Posts</i>	161
<i>Number of Impressions</i>	17,064
<i>Engagement Rate</i>	4.95%

As the project progresses to a more results-focused phase in its second half, new opportunities to reach target audiences will be created, such as live-posting in real-time of industry events, conferences, and exhibitions, as well as posting interactive polls, quizzes, or Q&A sessions related to renewable energy, climate change, or the project's developments to encourage audience participation, foster community engagement, and increase further increase our visibility on the platform. Furthermore, the focus on successful results and developments in the project will undoubtedly help to boost the profile and gain more followers in the coming months.

3.3.3 LinkedIn

For RESPONDENT, a LinkedIn company page was created at the outset of the project, and is available to view here: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/respondent-project-eu/?viewAsMember=true>

The RESPONDENT LinkedIn page has steadily increased its following since M1 of the project. The LinkedIn account is primarily used to raise awareness about the project and its results, facilitating knowledge transfer about the need for an increase of renewable energy sources to power the European energy sector.

Figure 6: RESPONDENT's LinkedIn profile

In terms of the KPIs for LinkedIn, the project has exceeded its target of 200 followers, currently boasting 285. The LinkedIn visitor analytics demonstrates that, within the first year of its existence, the page has attracted interests from a broad range of stakeholders and sectors, including Program and Project Management, Research, Engineering, and Information Technology. The engagement rate of the page is high at 4.5%, and the page is actively visited.

Table 9: LinkedIn analytics

LinkedIn analytics November 2022 – January 2024 (M1-M15)

<i>Number of Followers</i>	285
<i>Page Views</i>	1,278
<i>Page Visitors</i>	419
<i>Post Impressions</i>	22,960

An overview of the RESPONDENT LinkedIn page performance is presented in the above figures. This interim assessment of the performance indicates that the company page attracts engagement and interest from professionals and practitioners in the key fields relevant to the RESPONDENT project.

3.3.4 YouTube

The [RESPONDENT YouTube](#) channel was created in M6 of the project, and serves as an easily accessible platform for the project’s audio-visual highlights that can be easily embedded into social media posts and newsletters for increasing visibility and enhancing engagement and interaction with target audiences.

Branded RESPONDENT start and end cards were designed early on to be used across all videos for visual consistency, with a total of six videos having been created by M15. Although the KPI for YouTube of six videos has been achieved, the consortium is eager to continue producing audio-visual content in order to increase engagement with the RESPONDENT project and showcase our work in a visually attractive manner. Future planned video content includes infographic explainer videos, spotlight interviews with project partners following events, and summary videos of RESPONDENT’s pilot demonstrations.

Table 10: YouTube analytics

YouTube Analytics November 2022 – January 2024 (M1-M15)

<i>Number of Videos</i>	6
<i>Total Number of Views</i>	314
<i>Estimated Watch Time</i>	4.3 hours

Figure 7: RESPONDENT’s YouTube profile

3.4 Promotional Materials

A suite of first-class communications collateral was developed for RESPONDENT, including a pull-up banner, a leaflet, and a digital promotional presentation, all of which can be effectively utilised to promote the project at a wide range of events, conferences, and exhibitions. This material can be both viewed and downloaded

directly from the RESPONDENT website at the following link: <https://respondent-project.eu/dissemination-material/>.

As the project advances to next stages, new instalments of communications and training materials are expected to be developed, alongside the inclusion of updated project results. As we aim to minimise the environmental footprint of printed materials, the preference is given to electronic and digital materials, such as electronic posters, video materials and presentations.

4 Next Steps

As the project enters its second half, it will move into a new, more results-focused phase of dissemination and communication activities to reflect the increasing level of outcomes and solutions that the RESPONDENT partners produce. The development, demonstration, and validation of the innovative RESPONDENT solution suite and its individual components will naturally offer new opportunities for impactful dissemination.

All partners will continue to contribute to the core objective of the dissemination and communication strategy, ensuring that all results are made available to relevant stakeholders, and that the reasons for the results being of interest, benefit, and relevance to them is communicated effectively.

The ongoing activities described in the previous sections will continue to be carried out in from M15-M30 of the project. The availability of results will go hand in hand with intensified results-focused dissemination efforts involving all partners. The impact will be maximised through a broad range of activities including increased media outreach through press releases, the drafting and submission of publications, and uptake of the results among target groups and key stakeholders.

Table 11: Timeline of activities, M15-M30

Activity (Month)	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
<i>Task 7.1: Communication and Dissemination Activities, including Stakeholder Engagement</i>																
Monthly WP7 Calls																
Project website maintenance/updates																
Annual review of website																
X (Twitter) content																
LinkedIn content																
YouTube content																
Newsletters																
Review of promotional materials																
Submissions to publications (including drafting)																
Press release issued to media, media outreach																
Event attendance/hosting																
Media contacts database update																
Update of promotional materials (leaflet, poster, pull-up)																

	2-3/09/2024	International Conference on Renewable and Sustainable Energy (ICRSE-24)	Conference	Dublin, Ireland	https://after.org.in/event/index.php?id=2444295
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5 Conclusion

This deliverable has provided a detailed picture of the current communication and dissemination landscape of the RESPONDENT project at M15. This report builds on *D7.2 – Plan for Dissemination and Communication* (M6), and will feed into *D7.4 - Dissemination and Communication Report 2* (Final Report).

The main goal of this report was to present and analyse the dissemination and communication activities and achievements from M1 to M15 of the project. The first section of this deliverable has listed the dissemination activities that have been carried out thus far, including a measurement and analysis of performance, events attended, and networking efforts. The second part focused on the analysis of communication activities and effectiveness of the established channels to reach target audiences and relevant stakeholders, with the performance to date having been measured and analysed against the agreed KPIs in *D7.2 – Plan for Dissemination and Communication*.

The next steps have been outlined, and an indicative timeline has been presented for activities M15-M30 of the project. This report demonstrates that the project is on track to meet its communication and dissemination objectives, and that an intensification in any areas that are currently underperforming will be prioritised in the latter half of the project.

References

- [1] Adobe. (2022). Your guide to social media engagement rates. Learn target engagement rates for Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, and Twitter. Retrieved 12 January 2024 from:
<https://www.adobe.com/express/learn/blog/what-is-a-good-social-media-engagement-rate>

